

Supplement of

Optimizing CCN predictions through inferred modal aerosol composition – a boreal forest case study

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3 **Figure S1** (a) Lognormal size distributions calculated from the fit parameters obtained after applying the algorithm by Hussein
 4 et al. (2005) on observed size distributions. The solid lines represent the median values, while the shading indicates the
 5 percentiles. (b) Fitted versus observed total particle number concentration.

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8 **Figure S2** Number of data points for each season.

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12 **Figure S3** Monthly variation of activation diameter (D_{act}) for different supersaturation levels (SS) derived from aerosol number
 13 size distributions and observed CCN concentration. The plots display the median values (solid lines) and the corresponding

14 25th to 75th percentile range (error bars). Each panel represents a different supersaturation level ranging from 0.1% to 1.0%.
 15 The x-axis shows the months of the year, while the y-axis indicates D_{act} . Error bars represent the variability within each month.

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Table S1. Median activation diameters (D_{act}) in nanometers by season:

Seasons	D_{act} at SS = 0.1%	D_{act} at SS = 0.2%	D_{act} at SS = 0.3%	D_{act} at SS = 0.5%	D_{act} at SS = 1.0%
Spring	206	127	100	80	54
Summer	224	135	105	82	57
Autumn	224	137	109	84	56
Winter	206	129	104	82	55

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21 S1. Calculation of mass fraction of organic nitrate

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23 We have used the fragmentation pattern of nitrate in the ACSM to determine whether the detected nitrate
 24 is from ammonium nitrate or organic nitrate. The idea is based on Farmer et al. (2010) and in a nutshell, ammonium
 25 nitrate will yield a higher fraction of NO_2^+ as opposed to NO^+ compared to organic nitrate. NO_2^+ and NO^+ are the
 26 main peaks where nitrate will be distributed in. the fraction of nitrate that would be from organic nitrates (f_{ON}).
 27 The formula as mentioned in Farmer et al., 2010 is:

28

$$f_{ON} = \frac{(R_{obs} - R_{AN}) \times (1 + R_{ON})}{(R_{ON} - R_{AN}) \times (1 + R_{obs})} \quad (\text{S1})$$

29

- 30 - f_{ON} is the fraction of nitrate that is from organic nitrates
- 31 - R_{obs} is the $\text{NO}^+ : \text{NO}_2^+$ from ACSM measurements (nitrate fractions of m/z 30 and m/z 46)
- 32 - R_{AN} is the $\text{NO}^+ : \text{NO}_2^+$ that the AN calibration would yield
- 33 - R_{ON} is the $\text{NO}^+ : \text{NO}_2^+$ for pure organic nitrate

34

35 Here, it is assumed that $R_{AN} = 2$ since this would limit the number of negative values for f_{ON} , when $R_{ON} = 10$.
 36 The $R_{ON} = 10$ is to be expected from the NO_3 oxidation of α -pinene, which is assumed as a major source of ON
 37 at SMEAR II. Finally, using Eq. S1 with the R_{AN} and R_{ON} constants for 2016 onwards, a conservative guess for
 38 the time series for f_{ON} can be derived (Fig. S4). As f_{ON} exhibits a clear, and rather consistent seasonality, a seasonal
 39 mask could be retrieved using day-of-the year -based 3-month running median (Fig. S4). This day-of-the-year
 40 based mask is used further to estimate how much of the measured nitrate was present as ON and AN (the
 41 ammonium nitrate mass fraction $f_{AN} = 1 - f_{ON}$).

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Figure S4 Mask determining how much of the NO_3 ion is organic nitrate, and how much ammonium nitrate.

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Figure S5 Predicted ammonium ion (concentration necessary to achieve ion balance within the particles) and observed mass concentration of ammonium ion.

50 **S2. Demonstration of how scaling works**

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In this section, we describe the method (also referenced in Sect. 2.2.3 of the main article) used to scale the fitted size distribution to match the observations. This ensures that the total particle concentration, as well as the number of particles in each bin of the reconstructed size distribution (derived from fitted bimodal lognormal parameters), remains consistent with the observed size distribution (see Fig. S6). As a result, whether we use the original observed size distribution or the fitted bimodal size distribution when applying bulk chemical composition, the predicted CCN spectra remain the same. During scaling process, for each bin, the observed concentration is compared to the sum of the two fitted modes. If only one mode contributes, its concentration is

59 adjusted directly to match the observed value. When both modes contribute, the difference between observed and
 60 fitted totals is distributed proportionally based on each mode's relative contribution.

61 To better understand the process, scaling is explained in the steps as follows:

62 We have (in cm^{-3}):

63 $N_{\text{obs},i}$: Observed concentration in bin i

64 $N_{\text{fit,Ait},i}$: Fitted concentration for Aitken mode in bin i

65 $N_{\text{fit,acc},i}$: Fitted concentration for accumulation mode in bin i

66 $N_{\text{scaled,Ait},i}$: Scaled concentration for Aitken mode in bin i

67 $N_{\text{scaled,acc},i}$: Scaled concentration for accumulation in bin i

68 The scaling follows these steps:

69 Step 1: Scaling in the size distribution where only the Aitken mode has particles ($N_{\text{fit,acc},i} = 0$)

$$N_{\text{scaled,Ait},i} = N_{\text{fit,Ait},i} + (N_{\text{obs},i} - N_{\text{fit,Ait},i}) \quad (\text{S2})$$

$$N_{\text{scaled,acc},i} = 0 \quad (\text{S3})$$

70 Step 2: Scaling in the size distribution where only the accumulation mode has particles ($N_{\text{fit,Ait},i} = 0$)

$$N_{\text{scaled,acc},i} = N_{\text{fit,acc},i} + (N_{\text{obs},i} - N_{\text{fit,acc},i}) \quad (\text{S4})$$

$$N_{\text{scaled,Ait},i} = 0$$

72

73 Step 3: Scaling where both modes have contributions to the number of particles ($N_{\text{fit,Ait},i} \neq 0, N_{\text{fit,acc},i} \neq 0$);

74 Compute the fractional contributions of each mode

$$\text{fractional contribution of Aitken mode, } \mathcal{X}1_i = \frac{N_{\text{fit,Ait},i}}{N_{\text{fit,Ait},i} + N_{\text{fit,acc},i}} \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$\text{fractional contribution of accumulation mode, } \mathcal{X}2_i = \frac{N_{\text{fit,acc},i}}{N_{\text{fit,Ait},i} + N_{\text{fit,acc},i}} \quad (\text{S6})$$

$$\text{scaling factor, } \mathcal{X}_i = N_{\text{obs},i} - (N_{\text{fit,Ait},i} + N_{\text{fit,acc},i}) \quad (\text{S7})$$

$$\text{apply scaling, } N_{\text{scaled,Ait},i} = N_{\text{fit,Ait},i} + \mathcal{X}_i \cdot \mathcal{X}1_i \quad (\text{S8})$$

$$N_{\text{scaled,acc},i} = N_{\text{fit,acc},i} + \mathcal{X}_i \cdot \mathcal{X}2_i \quad (\text{S9})$$

Figure S6 An example of the size distribution scaling procedure. Bimodal fitting is done first and then the scaling aligns the reconstructed lognormal size distributions (black line in the left panel i.e. sum of fitted modes) with the observed distribution across binned diameters (D_p).

S3. Conservation of mass

In both the Nelder–Mead and DREAM-MCMC optimizations, the total aerosol mass is conserved across all chemical species (organics, inorganics, and eBC). Additionally, the eBC mass is fixed in both the Aitken and accumulation modes. This constraint reduces the optimization problem: we only vary the mass of one species (e.g., organics in the Aitken mode), while the remaining components are derived from conservation laws. For a given time step in the time series, let, $m_{\text{Ait}}^{\text{tot}}$ and $m_{\text{acc}}^{\text{tot}}$ are the total masses in Aitken and accumulation mode, respectively, obtained from bimodal size distribution and mass fractions. Similarly, let $m_{\text{BC,Ait}}$ and $m_{\text{BC,acc}}$ are the fixed eBC masses, then for each $m_{\text{org,Ait}}$ the optimization algorithm explore:

$$m_{\text{inorg,Ait}} = m_{\text{Ait}}^{\text{tot}} - (m_{\text{org,Ait}} + m_{\text{BC,Ait}}) \quad (\text{S10})$$

$$m_{\text{org,acc}} = m_{\text{org}}^{\text{tot}} - m_{\text{org,Ait}} \quad (\text{S11})$$

$$m_{\text{inorg,acc}} = m_{\text{acc}}^{\text{tot}} - (m_{\text{org,acc}} + m_{\text{BC,acc}}) \quad (\text{S12})$$

S4. Bayesian inference and MCMC

96 Bayesian inference is a rigorous method for quantifying uncertainty in model parameters (see also see
97 Gelman et al., 2013), using probability statements. Unknown parameters are treated as random variables with
98 some joint posterior probability distribution, which can be written using Bayes law as:
99

$$p(\theta|Y) = \frac{p(\theta)L(Y|\theta)}{p(Y)} \quad (\text{S13})$$

100 where $p(\theta)$ is the prior distribution which encompasses what is known about the parameters prior to observing
101 any data, $L(Y|\theta)$ is the likelihood function which measures how well the model fits observed data, and
102
103

$$p(Y) = \int p(\theta)p(Y|\theta)d\theta \quad (\text{S14})$$

104 is the marginal distribution of Y , which represents the probability of observing Y given all possible parameter
105 values θ . The result of conditioning the prior distribution with some observations is the posterior probability
106 distribution $p(\theta|Y)$, which represents the updated probability of the model parameters. Bayesian inference is
107 therefore a process of creating a probability model and iteratively updating that model based on some observations,
108 resulting in a best estimate of the parameters and knowledge about their uncertainty, sensitivity, and correlation
109 (in the case where θ is vector-valued).
110

111 Monte Carlo Markov Chain (MCMC) simulations are a methodology for sampling from posterior distributions.
112 Generally, they involve repeatedly and sequentially sampling θ such that each new draw depends only on the
113 previous sample and therefore forms a Markov chain, and correcting those draws so that the chain converges to
114 the target distribution. Many different algorithms have been proposed for generating and correcting chain samples.
115 Here we use the DiffereNtial Evolution Adaptive Metropolis Markov Chain Monte Carlo (DREAM-MCMC)
116 algorithm (Vrugt et al. 2009). This algorithm runs multiple chains simultaneously and adaptively updates the
117 proposal distribution using a randomized subset of the chains' joint history. It also supports large proposal jumps
118 and outlier rejection during the initial burn-in phase, which accelerate convergence. This type of self-adaptive
119 evolutionary strategy is particularly well suited to heavy-tailed or multi-modal posteriors, such as in this study
120 where different combinations of aerosol chemical composition and size distributions parameters could result in
121 similar CCN spectra.
122

123 124 **S5. Chain evolution in DREAM-MCMC**

125 As mentioned in sect. 2.2.3.1, we ran five DREAM-MCMC chains with 40,000 sampling steps each for
126 each CCN observation window. Figure S7 shows that for both windows there is an overprediction of the CCN
127 spectra when bulk composition is used, which is mostly corrected with the DREAM-MCMC optimized
128 parameters, showing that when size-segregated composition is combined with variability in the lognormal size
129 distribution parameters, most of the discrepancy between observed and predicted CCN can be resolved. Figures
130 S8 and S9 show examples of the chain evolution and the resulting posterior distributions for two distinct cases.

131
 132 **Figure S7.** Observed and optimized CCN spectra. The black line shows the observed spectra, the blue line represents the
 133 optimized spectra using the Nelder–Mead method with only size-segregated chemical composition as the optimized parameter,
 134 and the red line represents the DREAM-MCMC optimization where both size-segregated composition and size distribution
 135 parameters are optimized. Panel (a) corresponds to 2019-05-11 05:00:00, and panel (b) corresponds to 2019-10-15 07:00:00.
 136

137 The first example (Figure S7a and Figure S8) corresponds to a spring-time window, specifically 2019-05-11
 138 05:00:00. There is a higher total CCNc, and the DREAM-MCMC improves the closure at all super-saturations.
 139 All 5 chains converge well with \hat{R} -hat values very close to 1 for all parameters. The posterior distributions are
 140 relatively compact with the chain evolution indicating stable convergence, with broader distributions for $m_{\text{org,Ait}}$
 141 (in this note denoted as M_{org1}) and N_{Ait} (in this note denoted as N_1). There is a significant shift in the median of the
 142 posterior distribution of M_{org1} compared to the initial guess, whereas the posteriors of the size distribution
 143 parameters are centred on values very close to the median of the observations, suggesting that an increased mass
 144 fraction of organics in the Aitken mode is the key to better CCN closure for this time-step. However, the posterior
 145 distribution for M_{org1} is relatively wide, indicating less sensitivity to the exact value compared to the very tight
 146 posterior distributions for D_1 , N_1 , and D_2 (the diameters and number concentrations corresponding to Aitken and
 147 accumulation modes), which suggest that the closure is very sensitive to those three parameters.

148 In the second example (Figure S7b and Figure S9) the situation is more complex. This corresponds to a fall
 149 window, specifically 2019-10-15 07:00:00, where the total CCNc is lower. While DREAM-MCMC significantly
 150 improves the closure, it struggles more compared to the previous case, over-predicting at 0.1% SS and
 151 underpredicting at 0.2% and 0.3%. The chains show slower mixing and broader posteriors for several parameters,
 152 particularly M_{org1} , N_1 and D_2 . In this case medians of the posterior distributions are significantly shifted from the
 153 initial guesses for all parameters. The \hat{R} -hat values using all 5 chains are below 1.5 for all parameters but are
 154 larger for N_1 and D_1 (approx. 1.3 for both), indicating poorer mixing. Wider posteriors indicate possibly weak
 155 identifiability, meaning that multiple parameter combinations can yield similarly good agreement with the
 156 observed CCN spectra, pointing to stronger parameter correlations in the posterior. Here, M_{org1} is more poorly
 157 constrained than in the first case, but the number concentration parameters (N_1 and N_2) still play a more dominant
 158 role in reducing the CCN prediction.

159

160
 161 **Figure S8.** Chain evolution (right) and posterior distributions of the optimized parameters (left) from the DREAM-MCMC
 162 run. Each plot shows five parallel chains with 40,000 sampling steps. The vertical dashed line in the right panels marks the
 163 end of the burn-in period, and the posterior distributions on the left are taken from the final samples after burn-in which are
 164 used for posterior inference. Results correspond to observation 4200 (2019-05-11 05:00:00).

165

166

Figure S9. Chain evolution (right) and posterior distributions of the optimized parameters (left) from the DREAM-MCMC run. Each plot shows five parallel chains with 40,000 sampling steps. The vertical dashed line in the right panels marks the end of the burn-in period, and the posterior distributions on the left are based on the final samples after burn-in which are used for posterior inference. Results correspond to observation 5813 (2019-10-15 07:00:00).

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S6. Distribution of median absolute deviation (MAD)

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Figure S10 shows the probability density of median absolute deviation, MAD values fitted with chi-squared distributions for both the Aitken and accumulation modes. The results indicate that the variability is generally small, with distributions strongly centered close to zero and narrow tails. The fitted chi-squared parameters suggest that fluctuations in diameter and sigma are low, whereas number concentrations show comparatively larger spread. Overall, this analysis confirms that the derived parameters remain fairly stable within CCN cycle period, with occasional variability in particle number concentration.

179
 180 **Figure S10.** Chi-squared probability density functions (PDFs) fitted to the median absolute deviation (MAD) values of aerosol
 181 size distribution parameters calculated with respect to median of corresponding parameters during CCN cycle. The data
 182 represent entire 5 years period between 2016 to 2020. Panels show Aitken mode (top row) and accumulation mode (bottom
 183 row) MADs for mode diameter, geometric standard deviation (σ), and particle number concentration. The fitted parameters
 184 (degrees of freedom, ν , and scale) are reported in the legends. The fits are constrained to non-negative values to reflect the
 185 definition of MAD.

186

187 **S7. Distribution of normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) over brute-force sampled mass fraction**
 188 **bins of organic in Aitken mode ($f_{\text{org, Aitken}}$)**

189

190 To investigate how different combinations of mass fractions of different species in the Aitken and
 191 accumulation modes influence the model performance, we complemented the inverse modelling algorithms with
 192 a brute-force sampling approach. This allowed us to explore the full parameter space and examine the variation
 193 in normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) between measured and modelled CCN spectra across the entire
 194 dataset (2016-2020). Figure S11 illustrates the distribution of NRMSE values over this parameter space with
 195 respect to all samples of mass fraction of organics in Aitken mode ($f_{\text{org, Aitken}}$).

197

198 **Figure S11** Violin plots of the normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) between measured and modelled CCN spectra
 199 during optimization, grouped by the mass fraction of organics in the Aitken mode ($f_{\text{org, Aitken}}$).

200

201 S8. Calculation of activation diameter

202

203 The activation diameter, often referred to as the critical diameter, represents the minimum size of
 204 particles that can activate into cloud droplets at a given SS . This method estimates the activation diameter based
 205 on observed cloud condensation nuclei concentrations and particle number size distribution data.

206 Methodology

207 1. For a given CCN concentration at a particular supersaturation level:

- 208 ○ Find the bin where the cumulative particle concentration is either equal to or exceeds the CCN
 209 concentration (upper bound).
- 210 ○ Find the size bin where the cumulative particle concentration just falls below the CCN
 211 concentration.

212 2. Linear interpolation between size bins:

- 213 ○ The activation diameter lies between the sizes associated with the lower and upper bounds.
 214 Assuming that particle concentration changes linearly between these bins:

$$D_{\text{act}} = D_0 + \frac{N_{\text{CCN}} - N_0}{N_1 - N_0} \times (D_1 - D_0) \quad (\text{S15})$$

215 Where:

- 216 • D_{act} : Activation diameter
- 217 • D_0, D_1 : Diameters corresponding to the lower and upper cumulative concentrations, N_0 and N_1 ,
- 218 respectively.
- 219 • N_{CCN} : Observed CCN concentration.
- 220 • If the cumulative concentrations at the lower and upper bounds are identical ($N_0 = N_1$), the D_{act}
- 221 is assigned the diameter of the lower bound (D_0).

222

223

224 **Figure S12** Time series of sulfate ion mass concentration measured by the ACSM. Scatter points represent individual sulfate
 225 ion concentration values, while the black solid line indicates the linear regression fit. The slope and p -value of the regression
 226 are provided in the legend. The statistical significance of the trend is assessed at the 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$).

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Figure S13 Mass fractions of various chemical species during different seasons.

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 232 **Figure S14** Monthly median CCN concentrations at different supersaturations with shaded areas indicating the interquartile
 233 range.

234
 235 **Table S2.** Geometric mean bias (GMB) and Pearson's correlation coefficient (R) corresponding to different methods and
 236 supersaturations

Methods	GMB (R)				
	$SS = 0.1\%$	$SS = 0.2\%$	$SS = 0.3\%$	$SS = 0.5\%$	$SS = 1.0\%$
κ_{bulk}	1.56 (0.89)	1.19 (0.93)	1.19 (0.93)	1.34 (0.92)	1.34 (0.89)
$\kappa_{0.18}$	1.35 (0.85)	1.11 (0.93)	1.11 (0.93)	1.24 (0.93)	1.26 (0.90)
κ_{opt}	1.53 (0.89)	1.13 (0.93)	1.12 (0.94)	1.21 (0.94)	1.20 (0.93)
$\kappa_{\text{org}} = 0$	0.92 (0.83)	0.87 (0.87)	0.94 (0.87)	1.086 (0.89)	1.938 (0.87)
κ_{MCMC}	1.32 (0.85)	0.95 (0.97)	0.96 (0.99)	1.05 (0.99)	0.99 (0.99)

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 240 **Figure S15** Scatter plot illustrating the geometric mean bias (GMB) and Pearson correlation for different supersaturation (SS)
 241 levels, comparing four methods: κ_{bulk} , $\kappa_{0.18}$, and κ_{opt} , $\kappa_{\text{org}} = 0$. Each marker represents a different SS level, with size
 242 proportional to SS level, ranging from 0.1% to 1.0%. Bias is presented on the x-axis and correlation on the y-axis, with vertical

243 lines indicating perfect prediction (bias = 1). The plot shows the performance of each method across various *SS* levels, with
 244 annotations indicating underprediction (bias < 1) and overprediction (bias > 1).

245

246 S9. Performance Metrics of Various CCN Prediction Methods

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248 In figure S15, we looked at GMB but importantly, another quantity, the standard deviation (SD) of GMB
 249 provides insight into the robustness of each method: a lower SD indicates that the bias is consistent across cases,
 250 while a higher SD suggests larger variability in performance (Fig. S16). This makes it a key metric to consider
 251 when evaluating the stability of CCN prediction methods.

252

253

254 **Figure S16** Comparison of CCN prediction performance at supersaturations of 0.5 % and 1.0 % using different methods.
 255 Metrics shown are geometric mean bias (GMB), its standard deviation (SD), and correlation between predicted and observed
 256 CCN.

257

258 The results show that DREAM-MCMC (κ_{MCMC}) performs best overall, with a geometric mean bias very close to
 259 unity, extremely high correlation with observations, and the lowest spread. This indicates that it provides the most
 260 accurate and stable CCN predictions. The κ_{opt} method, which optimizes only size-segregated composition, ranks
 261 second: it achieves high correlation and relatively low variability, though the bias remains slightly above one,
 262 suggesting moderate overprediction. $\kappa_{\text{org}} = 0$ falls in the middle, with moderate bias, correlation, and variability,
 263 making it balanced but not particularly strong in any metric. The fixed $\kappa = 0.18$ approach performs similarly to
 264 $\kappa_{\text{org}} = 0$ but is slightly weaker, with somewhat lower correlation. Finally, κ_{bulk} performs the worst, showing the
 265 highest bias and systematic overprediction of CCN, along with only moderate correlation and spread.

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268
269 **Figure S17.** Seasonal variability of κ for Aitken and accumulation mode particles derived using Nelder–Mead optimization
270 (left) and DREAM–MCMC inversion (right). Boxes represent interquartile ranges, whiskers the 5th–95th percentiles, and
271 horizontal lines the medians.

272

273

274 **Table S3.** Median of optimized mass fractions of various chemical species in Aitken mode in different seasons

	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Organics	0.89	0.92	0.87	0.83
Inorganics	0.0017	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
eBC	0.10	0.075	0.13	0.17

275

276 **Table S4.** Median of optimized mass fractions of various chemical species in accumulation mode in different
277 seasons

	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Organics	0.54	0.71	0.57	0.46
Inorganics	0.37	0.23	0.32	0.40
eBC	0.09	0.06	0.10	0.14

278

279 **Table S5.** Mean of optimized mass fractions of various chemical species in Aitken mode in different seasons

	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Organics	0.70	0.75	0.72	0.69
Inorganics	0.20	0.19	0.16	0.16
eBC	0.1	0.06	0.11	0.15

280

281 **Table S6.** Mean of optimized mass fractions of various chemical species in Accumulation mode in different
282 seasons

	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
Organics	0.54	0.65	0.55	0.44

Inorganics	0.37	0.28	0.33	0.41
eBC	0.09	0.06	0.11	0.15

283

284 **Table S7.** Median mass fractions by group and optimization method.

285

Groups	Organics (Aitken)	Inorganics (Aitken)	BC (Aitken)	Organics (Acc)	Inorganics (Acc)	BC (Acc)
$\kappa_{\text{Aitken}} > \kappa_{\text{accumulation}}$ (MCMC)	0.11	0.78	0.11	0.69	0.23	0.08
$\kappa_{\text{Aitken}} > \kappa_{\text{accumulation}}$ (Nelder-Mead)	0.0004	0.87	0.12	0.68	0.23	0.087
$\kappa_{\text{accumulation}} > \kappa_{\text{Aitken}}$ (MCMC)	0.87	0.04	0.09	0.54	0.37	0.088
$\kappa_{\text{accumulation}} > \kappa_{\text{Aitken}}$ (Nelder-Mead)	0.91	0.0001	0.09	0.09	0.58	0.087

286

287 **Table S8.** Median κ and fraction of data points by group and optimization method.

288

Groups	Median κ_{Aitken}	Median $\kappa_{\text{accumulation}}$	Fraction of data
$\kappa_{\text{Aitken}} > \kappa_{\text{accumulation}}$ (MCMC)	0.47	0.21	0.54
$\kappa_{\text{Aitken}} > \kappa_{\text{accumulation}}$ (Nelder-Mead)	0.50	0.20	0.23
$\kappa_{\text{accumulation}} > \kappa_{\text{Aitken}}$ (MCMC)	0.13	0.27	0.46
$\kappa_{\text{accumulation}} > \kappa_{\text{Aitken}}$ (Nelder-Mead)	0.11	0.26	0.77

289

290

291 **S10. Insights on effect of the assumption of fixed eBC mass in both modes**

292

293 The CCN spectra obtained using bulk chemical composition generally depicts overprediction from the
294 observations, with the largest bias at both lowest supersaturation (0.1%) and the highest supersaturation (1.0%).
295 A way to reduce this overprediction is to have a size-segregated composition that makes the Aitken mode as low
296 in hygroscopicity as possible. As a conservative approach, when eBC is fixed only in accumulation mode (leaving
297 no eBC mass in Aitken mode), the 5 year averaged (median) NRMSE remains almost similar at 0.28 (a little on
298 higher side), while Aitken kappa is a bit higher as a non-hygroscopic element i.e. eBC is now completely in
299 accumulation mode. In another approach, we allowed eBC to vary as an additional optimization parameter along
300 with organics in the Aitken mode instead of keeping its mass fraction fixed in both modes. As expected, this
301 adjustment lowers the NRMSE from 0.28 to 0.23, while the optimized κ remains nearly unchanged, but a little on
302 lower side than the setup we use (see Table S10). Interesting to note that, this setup suggest that there should be
303 70% eBC in Aitken mode which seems unrealistic. Complementary results from DREAM-MCMC optimization
304 (optimizing modal BC mass fraction while considering variability of lognormal parameters of size distribution
305 during CCN cycle, see Table S11) of the same problem suggests similar results with around on an average 41%
306 BC in Aitken mode – again a very high number considering the expected aerosol sources at the cite.

307

308

309 **Table S9.** Median of optimized mass fractions of various chemical species in Aitken and accumulation mode
 310 when all eBC are kept in accumulation mode – results from Nelder-Mead

Organics (Aitken)	Inorganics (Aitken)	eBC (Aitken)	Organics (accumulation)	Inorganics (accumulation)	eBC (accumulation)
0.99	0.01	0.00	0.59	0.43	0.10

311

312 **Table S10.** Median of optimized κ in different seasons when all eBC are kept in accumulation mode– results from
 313 Nelder-Mead

	Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
κ_{Aitken}	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12
$\kappa_{\text{accumulation}}$	0.27	0.21	0.24	0.29

314

315 **Table S11.** Median of optimized mass fractions of various chemical species in Aitken and accumulation mode
 316 when eBC is also an optimized parameter

	Organics (Aitken)	Inorganics (Aitken)	eBC (Aitken)	Organics (accumulation)	Inorganics (accumulation)	eBC (accumulation)
Nelder- Mead	0.26	0.046	0.70	0.62	0.31	0.07
MCMC	0.32	0.27	0.41	0.63	0.30	0.07

317

318 **S11. Optimizing organic properties**

319

320 We conducted additional inverse-closure sensitivity studies to assess how the assumed organic aerosol
 321 properties influence the optimized parameters. Three types of inverse-closure tests were performed:

- 322 a) Using bulk-composition but optimizing only the organic density, ρ_{org} and organic hygroscopicity
 323 parameter, κ_{org}
- 324 b) Optimizing ρ_{org} and κ_{org} while also accounting for variability of size distribution lognormal parameters
 325 during CCN cycles
- 326 c) Optimizing $m_{\text{org,Ait}}$, ρ_{org} and κ_{org} but not accounting for variability of size distribution lognormal
 327 parameters during CCN cycles

328 In all tests, κ_{org} was varied between 0.05 and 0.15, while ρ_{org} ranged from 1000 to 3000 kg m⁻³. Method (a)
 329 resulted in a lower NRMSE but yielded a median optimized organic density of 1000 kg m⁻³, which appears
 330 unrealistic. Method (b) produced a slightly higher NRMSE (0.085 compared to 0.079 from κ_{MCMC}) but provided
 331 a more realistic optimized organic density of 2179 kg m⁻³, exhibiting clear seasonal variability, with a minimum
 332 of approximately 1750 kg m⁻³ in summer. This value is notably higher than the 1500 kg m⁻³ assumed in the
 333 original inverse-closure approach. Both methods produced optimized κ_{org} values between 0.05 and 0.07,
 334 depending on the season. Overall, we obtained a reasonable estimate of optimized κ_{org} however, due to certain

335 unknown factors, the optimized ρ_{org} values remain physically implausible. In contrast, method (c) produced highly
 336 consistent and realistic results, as summarized in the table below.

337 **Table S12:** Median of optimized quantities in different seasons when $m_{\text{org,Ait}}$, ρ_{org} and κ_{org} are considered the for
 338 optimization while not accounting for variability of size distribution lognormal parameters

	κ_{Aitken}	$\kappa_{\text{accumulation}}$	$\kappa_{\text{org}}^{\text{Aitken}}$	$\kappa_{\text{org}}^{\text{accumulation}}$	ρ_{org} (kg m ⁻³)
Spring	0.16	0.24	0.07	0.07	1228.56
Summer	0.15	0.18	0.07	0.07	1304.12
Autumn	0.13	0.23	0.07	0.08	1307.69
Winter	0.11	0.26	0.06	0.07	1224.46

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